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The Effect of Teachers' Performance on the Academic Achievement of Learners as a Basis for an Action Plan for Performance Improvement in the Schools Division of the City of Ilagan

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Abstract

Teacher quality is globally recognized as a key determinant of student learning outcomes and overall educational effectiveness. However, limited empirical evidence exists in the local context linking teachers' performance, as measured by the Results-Based Performance Management System–Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (RPMS-PPST), with the actual academic achievement of learners. This study examined the effect of teachers' performance on the academic achievement of learners in the Schools Division of the City of Ilagan as a basis for an action plan to enhance performance. Anchored on RPMS-PPST, the research sought to determine teachers' performance levels, differences across positions and school levels, their perceptions of RPMS-PPST, and the relationship between performance ratings and learners' achievement. Employing a descriptive research design, the study involved 477 elementary and 390 secondary public school teachers. Data were gathered through questionnaires, informal interviews, and documentary analysis, and analyzed using descriptive statistics, Pearson's correlation, and t-tests.

Findings revealed that both elementary and secondary Teachers I-III and Master Teachers I-II obtained *Very Satisfactory* performance ratings, with no significant difference between the elementary and secondary counterparts. The Division Academic Performance Survey showed that most elementary schools were *Moving Towards Mastery* (mean = 70.71), while all secondary schools were at *Average Mastery* (mean = 49.63). Teachers' performance significantly affected secondary learners' achievement ($p = 0.0343$) but showed no significant effect on elementary learners' results ($p = 0.3473$). Teachers expressed strong agreement with RPMS-PPST indicators across the ratee–rater relationship, portfolio preparation, and classroom observation, though significant perception differences existed between elementary and secondary teachers.

The study concludes that while teachers demonstrate high performance and positive perceptions of RPMS-PPST, its impact is more evident in the achievement of secondary learners. Recommendations include strengthening performance monitoring and coaching, sustaining academic performance surveys, and refining RPMS-PPST implementation through targeted interventions. Findings offer insights for policy-makers and school leaders in aligning teacher development with improved student outcomes.

Keywords: Teacher performance, academic achievement, RPMS-PPST, perception, performance monitoring, learning outcomes

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